

Modified Davies Equation

B. PRASAD

Chemistry Department, Patna University, Patna

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The modified Davies equation is

$$\log \gamma_i = -\frac{AZ_i^2 \sqrt{\mu}}{1 + \sqrt{\mu}} + \beta_i \mu,$$

where β_i does not depend on its valency alone. β_i is independent of the composition of the ion atmosphere to a large extent, but changes when there is complete change in composition of ion atmosphere. The equation is generally valid upto $\mu = 0.1$, but in some cases it works up to $\mu = 0.2$.

ACTIVITY coefficient of an ion can be represented as $\log \gamma_i = -\frac{AZ_i^2 \sqrt{\mu}}{1 + \sqrt{\mu}} + \beta_i \mu$. For HX we can write

$$\log \gamma_{H^+} \gamma_{X^-} = -\frac{2A\sqrt{\mu}}{1 + \sqrt{\mu}} + (\beta_{H^+} + \beta_{X^-})\mu.$$

Davies¹ proposed $\log \gamma_i = -AZ_i^2 \left(\frac{\sqrt{\mu}}{1 + \sqrt{\mu}} - 0.2\mu \right)$.

In other words he proposed that β_i should depend only on the charge of the ion. If Davies equation was correct then $\beta = \beta_{H^+} + \beta_{X^-}$ would be equal to 0.2076 or roughly 0.2 at 25° for all acids of the type HX. It is clear from Table-1 that β is not independent of X.

The e.m.f. of both the cells is given by the equation ;

$$E = E^0 + \frac{RT}{F} \ln m_{H^+} m_{Cl^-} - \frac{RT}{F} \times 2.3026 \frac{2A\sqrt{\mu}}{1 + \sqrt{\mu}} + \frac{RT}{F} \times 2.3026 \beta \mu \quad \dots(1)$$

The values of E^0 and β were found³ from cell (C₁). The e.m.f. of the cell (C₂) is calculated on the assumption that β is same for cell (C₂) i.e. independent of the composition of ion atmosphere. The difference³ in the measured and calculated values was of the order of

0.1 mv up to $\mu < 0.07$ and 0.2 mv when $\mu > 0.07$ and $\mu < 0.1$. The

concentration of H⁺ in the cell (C₂) never went below 2×10^{-3} and that of Cl⁻ below 10^{-2} .

Covington¹⁰ studied glass electrode cells equivalent to cell (C₃) given below.

The ionic strength of the cells was maintained at 0.1 by him. The e.m.f. values of the cells calcuted by us¹¹ on the assumption of β being independent of the composition of ion atmosphere are given in Table-2. It may be noted that Covington had studied the cells with a different point of view.

TABLE 1

Author	HX	Value of β at 25°C
Harned and Ehlers ²	HCl	0.490
Sharma, Sahu and Prasad ³	HCl	0.475
Covington and Prue ⁴	HCl	0.450
Gupta, Hill and Ives ⁵	HCl	0.422
Hetzer, Robinson and Bates ⁶	HBr	0.610
Sinha and Prasad ⁷	HBr	0.539
Lal and Prasad ⁸	HSCN	1.048

The next question which arises is whether β_i will be independent of the composition of ion atmosphere. To check this, cells C₁ and C₂ were studied. In cells C₁ and C₂, Q.H. stands for quinhydrone. M in cell C₂ stands for Mg, Ca, Sr, and Ba.

TABLE 2

m ₁	m ₂	Obs.e.m.f. in mv.	Cal.e.m.f. in mv.	Difference
0.0750	0.0083	9.71	9.63	0.1
0.0500	0.0167	22.72	22.49	0.2
0.0250	0.0250	43.42	43.01	0.4
0.0100	0.0300	68.85	68.32	0.5
0.0050	0.0317	87.31	86.75	0.6

In Convington's work concentration of H^+ did not go below 5×10^{-3} and that of Cl^- below 6×10^{-3} . Assuming that β is independent of the composition of the ion atmosphere the dissociation constant of some acids have been recalculated. Harned and Ehlers² had studied the cell

The same authors² in order to measure the dissociation constant (K) of acetic acid also studied the cell (C₅) where Ac stands for acetate.

They had to assume a rough value of K in order to calculate an accurate value of K. If β is assumed to be independent of the composition of ion atmosphere it is not necessary to make any such assumption. The e.m.f. of the cell (C₄) as well cell (C₅) is given by

$$E + \frac{2.30259 RT}{F} \log m_{H^+} m_{Cl^-} - \frac{2.30259 RT}{F} \frac{2A\sqrt{\mu}}{1 + \sqrt{\mu}} = E^0 - \frac{2.30259 RT}{F} \beta \mu \quad \dots(2)$$

E^0 and β are found from cell (C₄). In cell (C₅) m_{Cl^-} is known, β is assumed to be the same as in cell (C₄). By assigning a rough value to μ corresponding value of m_{H^+} is found from equation (2). Thereafter a new value of μ is found from $\mu = m_{H^+} + m_2 + m_3^+$. The process is repeated till m_{H^+} is constant to the eighth place of decimal. At this stage, m_{Ac^-} and m_{HA^0} are calculated from $m_{Ac^-} = m_2 + m_{H^+}$, $m_{HA^0} = m_1 - m_{H^+}$. Further

$$\log \frac{m_{H^+} m_{Ac^-}}{m_{HA^0}} - \frac{2A\sqrt{\mu}}{1 + \sqrt{\mu}} = \log K - b\mu \quad \dots(3)$$

The left hand side of the equation in which all the quantities are known, plotted against μ gives a straight line up to $\mu=0.18$. From this line K is calculated¹. The value of K is the same as that found by Harned and Ehlers. This further justifies that β in these experiments is independent of the composition of ion atmosphere. It may be noted that concentration of H^+ is about 10^{-6} and that of Cl^- ion varies from 4×10^{-3} to 9×10^{-2} .

Second dissociation constant of oxalic acid also has been recalculated^{1,2} on the basis of β being independent of the composition of ion atmosphere from cell (C₆) of Harned and Fallon^{1,3} and cell (C₇) of Pinching and Bates^{1,4}.

$H_2 | NaHOx(m_1) Na_2Ox(m_2) NaCl(m_3) AgCl | Ag \quad (C_6)$
 $H_2 | KHOOx(m_1) Na_2Ox(m_2) NaCl(m_3) AgCl | Ag \quad (C_7)$
 The pK value of the two sets of authors as calculated by them differ in the second place of decimal. The values of pK recalculated^{1,2} from the work of the two authors on the basis of β being independent of the composition of ion atmosphere differ in the third place of decimal. Here also it is not necessary to assume a rough value of pK. In cells (C₆) and (C₇) the concentration of H^+ was never less than 2.4×10^{-6} and that of Cl^- never less than 5×10^{-3} .

The value of B in the equation (4) comes out to be the same for the two sets of measurements. This further justifies that β is independent of the composition of ion atmosphere.

$$\log K_2 = \log \frac{m_{H^+} + m_{Ox^{2-}}}{m_{HOx^-}} - \frac{4A\sqrt{\mu}}{1 + \sqrt{\mu}} + B\mu \quad \dots (4)$$

In all the above cases there has been no drastic change in ion atmosphere. Hydrogen ion is always surrounded by chloride ion. In addition some other ions like acetate, bioxalate or oxalate are also present. Similarly chloride ion is always surrounded by hydrogen ion. In addition some ions like sodium, potassium, magnesium, barium etc. are also present. Bioxalate ion is always surrounded by hydrogen ion in addition to some other ions.

Hence the conclusion that if there is no drastic change in the composition of ion atmosphere then β will be independent of the composition of the ion atmosphere, is justified.

To test as to what will happen if there is a drastic change, the cells of the type

The e.m.f. of these cells is given by

$$E - E^0 + \frac{RT}{F} \ln \frac{m_2}{m_1} = - \frac{RT}{F} \ln K_w + \frac{RT}{F} \times 2.3026 (\beta_{OH^-} - \beta_{Cl^-}) \mu$$

In case of any cell all the quantities on the left hand side are known. When L.H.S. is plotted against μ we should get a straight line, whose slope would be independent of M⁺ if β_{OH^-} and β_{Cl^-} are independent of ion atmosphere. The slopes^{1,6} differ with M. Hence if a drastic change is made in the ion atmosphere the postulate will not work.

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